

Phenotypic Response of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* to Different Hydrogen Ion Concentrations of an Herbal Drug

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ABSTRACT

Herbal drugs which are used as alternative sources of medicine interact with gut microbiota where the pH conditions vary from an acidic pH in the stomach to a more alkaline pH in the large intestine. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of different hydrogen ion conditions of the herbal drug, Goko Alcoholic Bitters (GAB) on the virulence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Overnight culture of *P. aeruginosa* was treated with GAB at three different pH conditions (neutral (7.0), alkaline (9.0), and acidic 4.0)). Growth response, biofilm, antibiotic susceptibility, and serum bactericidal effect on GAB-treated and untreated *P. aeruginosa* was done. In the growth response study to different concentrations of GAB (control, 0.006, 0.010, 0.018, 0.030, 0.045 g/ml) at neutral, alkaline and acidic pH, growth ($6.6 \pm 0.9 \times 10^5$, $1.7 \pm 0.5 \times 10^5$, $1.8 \pm 0.3 \times 10^5$, $8.1 \pm 1.3 \times 10^4$, $9.9 \pm 1.6 \times 10^4$, $6.6 \pm 0.9 \times 10^4$ CFU/ml), ($5.9 \pm 2.0 \times 10^5$, $1.5 \pm 0.9 \times 10^4$, $3.0 \pm 1.5 \times 10^4$, $1.8 \pm 0.2 \times 10^4$, $2.8 \pm 0.9 \times 10^4$, $5.5 \pm 3.9 \times 10^4$ CFU/ml), and ($4.9 \pm 2.3 \times 10^5$, $2.5 \pm 1.5 \times 10^4$, $1.6 \pm 1.1 \times 10^4$, $1.0 \pm 0.8 \times 10^4$, $1.0 \pm 0.2 \times 10^4$, $1.7 \pm 0.2 \times 10^3$ CFU/ml) respectively was observed. Indicating a decrease, increase and decrease in growth as the concentration of GAB increased at neutral, alkaline, and acidic pH respectively. Generally, the highest concentration (0.045 g/ml) of the different pH conditions showed the highest sensitivity while the lowest showing reduced sensitivity in the study. The untreated bacteria had >27 mm for both gentamycin and ceftriaxone which represent they were sensitive. For the neutral pH, all GAB concentrations were sensitive to both antibiotics. Similar observations were recorded in the acidic pH, however, all the concentrations had zones of inhibition of above 24 mm for both antibiotics. For the alkaline condition, all concentrations were resistant to gentamycin except the highest concentration (14 mm) which was intermediately sensitive. The ceftriaxone was resistant to only the lowest concentration but moderately sensitive to the remaining concentrations of GAB. The level of biofilm induced by the herbal drug is directly proportional to the different concentrations of the herbal drug (i.e. higher concentrations induced more biofilm). For the serum test, the highest growth was observed in the alkaline condition followed by the acid pH and then negative control. Lower pH conditions (acidic [pH 4.0] and alkaline [pH 7.0]) reduced the *P. aeruginosa* growth the most but induced the maximum levels of biofilm and serum resistance compared to the control in a concentration-dependent mode.

Keywords: Herbal drugs; *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*; Antibiotic resistance; Serum resistance; Hydrogen ion concentration; Biofilm

INTRODUCTION

Pseudomonas aeruginosa formerly known as *Pseudomonas pyocyanea* is a gram-negative, motile rod-shaped bacterium. It thrives in immunocompromised individuals with cystic fibrosis, severe burns among others [1]. A recent systematic review showed that *P. aeruginosa* is the fourth most prevalent gram-negative bacteria in Africa with an overall prevalence of approximately 11% [2]. The bacterium resists several antimicrobials due to its ability to produce proteases, toxins, and resistance to phagocytosis. Several strains of *P.*

aeruginosa are sensitive to quinolones, cephalosporins, gentamicin, colistin, polymyxin, streptomycin, and carbenicillin [3].

The ability of *P. aeruginosa* to cause these life-threatening diseases is due to its ability to survive in the host especially in the early stages of the infection mainly because of the toxins it secretes and the virulence factors produced. Some key virulence factors employed by *P. aeruginosa* are: Lipopolysaccharides (LPS), flagella and type 4 pili, proteases, Type 3 Secretion Systems (T3SS), Quorum Sensing (QS), biofilm formation, pyocyanin, lipid A

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among others [4,5]. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infections pose a serious challenge to therapeutic management using conventional antimicrobial agents. This is due to the adaptive mechanisms of the bacterium to tolerate drugs using intrinsic, acquired, and adaptive mechanisms [6]. A crucial virulence factor responsible for the survival and adaptation of this bacterium is biofilm [7] which is made up of a complex community of bacteria enclosed within an extracellular polysaccharide matrix [8]. The formation of biofilm requires several interconnected signal transduction pathways called quorum sensing. This mechanism permits each bacterium within the community to communicate at a cell-to-cell level. The process results in the production of secretory molecules known as autoinducers that cause the transcription of population-dependent genes responsible for physiological adaptation [9,10].

Certain environmental conditions such as pH, temperature, osmotic pressure, dissolved gases are essential for bacteria growth. Bacteria cannot grow and reproduce within a certain range of these conditions even when other nutritional requirements necessary for their growth are intact. The first component of the bacterial cell to be affected by a change in pH is the cytoplasmic membrane [11]. Hydrogen ion concentration is a crucial physicochemical factor that determines the population of a bacterial community [12]. Their proteins and enzymes are denatured in extreme pH leading to alteration in the ionic charges in the bacterial cell which results in the loss of the catalytic properties of the enzymes, halt in metabolism, and eventually death of the bacterial cell. At extreme acidic pH, the hydrogen bonds between deoxyribonucleic acid molecules are broken down, hydrolysis of lipids occurs at extreme alkaline pH thereby leading to the impairment of energy production [12]. These physicochemical factors are explored by drug design companies to achieve an optimum bactericidal effect.

Owing to the rise in infectious disease, antimicrobial resistance, and high cost of living in developing nations, most individuals resort to the use of herbal alternatives to treat infections and other diseases [13,14]. Herbal therapy has been an ancient practice in Nigeria. Different roots, seeds, leaves, barks are used for the treatment of different ailments. In Nigeria, the use of alcoholic bitters however became popular in 2007 with the introduction of Alomo bitters [12]. With the high patronage it received, there has been a proliferation of different unlicensed brands of alcoholic bitters prepared under unhygienic conditions and containing substances that could be potentially hazardous to the consumers.

There is an increase in the consumption of locally made herbal drugs in Nigeria. It has become imperative to determine the appropriate conditions for their effectiveness in the treatment of certain diseases caused by microorganisms especially because certain factors such as pH, may not have been taken into account during the preparation of the drug. The herbal drug used for this study is Goko cleanser which is a herbal mixture containing the following active ingredients: *Allium sativum*, *Cajanus cajan*, *Saccharum officinalis*, *Vernonia amygdalina*, and ethanol. *Cajanus cajan* also known as the pigeon pea, from the family Fabaceae is a perennial legume with excellent biological and medicinal properties. The leaves of *C. cajan* are rich in flavonoids, stilbenes, saponins, tannins, terpenoids, and lots more [15,16]. Extracts of *Cajanus cajan* possess *in vivo* antimicrobial activity against some microbial strains that include *P. aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Escherichia coli*, *Candida albicans* among others [16,17]. Coumarin, a new natural cajanuslactone isolated from the

leaves of *C. cajan*, is potentially antibacterial [18,16].

The goal of this research was to evaluate the phenotypic response of *P. aeruginosa*, using growth, biofilm formation, serum bactericidal challenge, and antibiotic sensitivity, exposed to a commonly used (Goko alcoholic bitters) herbal drug under different induced pH conditions. The study succeeded in showing that there was a directly proportional relationship between the growth of *P. aeruginosa* in an alkaline medium but inverse in acid conditions. The basic concentrations also induce resistance in *P. aeruginosa* while the acid-treated media induce sensitivity in the bacterium.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Drugs

The herbal drug used in this study, Goko alcoholic bitters, GAB, was purchased from Mile 3 market, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria while the antibiotic discs, Gentamycin (10 µg) and Ceftriaxone (30 µg).

Test organism

P. aeruginosa PAO1 was obtained from Lahor Research Laboratories, Edo State, Nigeria, and stored in 50% glycerol and kept at -20°C.

Media preparation

Tryptic Soy Agar (TSA), Mueller-Hinton Agar (MHA), and Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) were prepared according to the manufacturer's instruction and autoclaved at 15 psi or 121°C for 15 minutes. The agar was allowed to cool to 50°C and aseptically poured into a sterile Petri dish and allowed to solidify at room temperature (25°C) on a vibration-free surface then stored at 4°C for subsequent use. The broth was stored at room temperature until further use.

Preparation of acidic and alkaline solutions

The acidic or basic solutions were prepared by adding 0.5 M hydrochloric acid (HCl) or 0.5 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) to tryptone soy broth until the desired pH is achieved. The pH was checked intermittently until the pH got to 4.0 and 9.0 for acidic and alkaline conditions respectively. The TSB pH is 7.2 hence to obtain a neutral pH HCl was added to adjust the pH to 7.0.

Growth response assay

Overnight culture of *P. aeruginosa* at optical density 0.5 was diluted serially to 10⁶ (equivalent to 10³ CFU/ml of the bacterium when enumerated on nutrient agar) in acidic, basic, and neutral TSB medium. Two milliliters of the serially diluted overnight inoculum (10⁶) from the acidic, basic, and neutral conditions were aseptically dispensed into six sterile bijoux bottles. Five different concentrations of GAB, 0.06 g/ml, 0.045 g/ml, 0.030 g/ml, 0.018 g/ml, 0.010 g/ml and a negative control was added to each of the tubes for all conditions. They were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. To enumerate the bacteria in the overnight cultures, they were serially diluted to obtain discrete colonies on the TSA which were incubated at 37°C for 18 h and observed for growth.

Biofilm assay

Overnight culture of *P. aeruginosa* at optical density 0.5 was diluted serially to 10⁶ (equivalent to 10³ CFU/ml of the bacterium when enumerated on nutrient agar) in acidic, basic, and neutral TSB medium. Two milliliters of the serially diluted overnight inoculum (1,000,000 CFU/ml) from the acidic, basic, and neutral conditions was aseptically dispensed into a 24-well polystyrene plate. Five different concentrations of GAB, 0.06 g/ml, 0.045 g/ml, 0.030

g/ml, 0.018 g/ml, 0.010 g/ml and a negative control was added to each of the tubes for all conditions. They were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. No GAB was added to the negative control. Supernatants were removed, and some residual culture media, as well as loosely adhered bacteria, were removed by vigorously tapping the plate on a tray. Wells were washed three times with normal saline to get rid of any remaining non-adherent bacterial cells and media. Plates were air-dried at about 45°C for 1 h. The plate wells were then stained with 1000 µl of 5% crystal violet solution for 15 minutes at room temperature. After the stain was removed, plates were washed twice in normal saline and dried overnight. Plates were then incubated in 200 µl of 95% ethanol for 10 minutes to solubilize the crystal violet stain. Finally, the attachment of bacteria was quantified by measuring the absorbance of the crystal violet at 595 nm. The experiment was performed in triplicate on at least three separate occasions.

Serum resistance test

Serum bactericidal effect on GAB exposed *P. aeruginosa* was performed by modification of the protocol in Posdchun [19]. The organism was grown in TSB to the mid-log phase (OD = 0.5) and incubated with 30% pooled normal human serum and heat-inactivated human serum (normal human serum heated to boiling temperature for 3 minutes) for 12 h. Optimal activation was achieved by heating the serum in a sterile test tube up to boiling for 3 minutes. Several concentrations of serum from 10% to 90% were tested, and 40% was determined as the most efficient concentration. Bacteria were serially diluted and plated immediately after inoculation on nutrient agar at 12 h intervals for 48 h. The serum bactericidal effect was determined by enumerating the bacteria in the overnight cultures on TSA which were incubated at 37°C for 18 h and observed for growth.

Antibiotic susceptibility assay of GAB-treated *P. aeruginosa*

Discrete colonies from a pure culture were inoculated into peptone

water and incubated at 37°C for 16 h. The turbidity of the incubated cultures was standardized against 0.5 McFarland's standard using sterile peptone water to obtain comparable turbidities. Antibiotics susceptibility testing was done using the conventional gold standard disc diffusion method by Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute [20]. Mueller-Hinton Agar (MHA) plate was inoculated with the aid of a sterile cotton swab stick dipped into the standardized bacterial culture and allowed to dry. Antibiotic discs were aseptically placed on the surface of the MHA. The cultured MHA plate was incubated at 37°C for 16 h and the zone of antibiotic clearance was measured.

Statistics

All experiments were carried out in triplicate and data are represented as Mean ± Standard Deviation (SD). Where appropriate, data analyses were carried out using an unpaired t-test in which a two-tailed p-value was determined using GraphPad Prism Software Version 8.0.2, San Di-ego, CA. The analyses were considered to be significant at a 95% Confidence Interval (CI) at a p-value less than 0.05.

RESULTS

Growth response of *P. aeruginosa* in GAB at different pH

Figures 1-3 represent the growth response of *P. aeruginosa* in various concentrations of GAB augmented with different pH conditions; neutral (pH=7.0), alkaline (pH=9.0), and acidic (pH=4.0) conditions respectively. There is a significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in the growth of *P. aeruginosa* across the concentrations in the neutral condition compared to control without GAB. The same trends were noted in the alkaline and acidic induced conditions; however, the level of growth was much lower in pH augmented conditions. For the acidic and neutral conditions, the bacteria growth showed an inverse relationship with the concentrations (i.e. the higher the concentration, the lower the bacterial growth) of GAB while the reverse of this observation was noted in the basic pH.

Antibiotic sensitivity of GAB-treated and untreated *P. aeruginosa*

To investigate the antibiotic sensitivity level of the bacteria after treatment with GAB, the antibiotic susceptibility assay was performed on the treated and untreated *P. aeruginosa* using gentamycin and ceftriaxone discs. Varying degrees of susceptibility patterns were observed to the different antibiotics. The untreated bacteria (control) demonstrated zones of inhibition above 27 mm

for both antibiotics used which represent they were sensitive. For the neutral pH, all GAB concentrations were sensitive to both antibiotics, however, they were all lower (<26 mm) than the control (>26 mm). Similar observations were recorded in the acidic pH, however, all the concentrations had zones of inhibition of ≥ 24 mm for both antibiotics. For the alkaline condition, all concentrations showed resistant phenotype to gentamycin except the highest concentration (14 mm) which was intermediately sensitive. The ceftriaxone was resistant to only the lowest concentration but

moderately sensitive to the remaining concentrations of GAB. Generally, the highest concentration (0.045 g/ml) of the different pH conditions showed the highest sensitivity while the lowest showing reduced sensitivity in the study (Table 1).

Effect of GAB on biofilm formation of *P. aeruginosa* at different pH

The production of biofilm by *P. aeruginosa* exposed to different concentrations of GAB supplemented with neutral, alkaline, and acidic pH is shown in Figures 4-6 respectively. The three pH conditions tested induced the same pattern of biofilm production in the study organism. The level of biofilm induced by the herbal drug is directly proportional to the different concentrations of the herbal drug (i.e. higher concentrations induced more biofilm). However, the acid and alkaline conditions show a slightly higher level of biofilm than the neutral condition. In all cases, the GAB-

supplemented conditions showed a significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher level of biofilm compared to the unsupplemented control except the 0.010 g/ml which was still higher but not significant ($p = 0.0696$).

Serum resistance of *P. aeruginosa* treated with GAB

Figures 7A and B show the serum efficacy against the treated and untreated *P. aeruginosa*. The trend graph shows that the negative control has the slowest growth rate followed by the acidic condition and then the alkaline pH (Figure 7A). The three conditions troughed at 36 h and further increased in bacterial growth at 48 h for acid and negative control while the alkaline condition decreased. Using the optimal serum bactericidal condition which was obtained at 36 h, the highest growth was observed in the alkaline condition followed by the acid pH and then negative control (Figure 7B). The only significant observation noted was between the alkaline pH and negative control ($p = 0.0195$).

Table 1: Antibiotics sensitivity of *P. aeruginosa* at different pH in GAB.

		Concentrations of herbal drugs (g/ml)					
		Control	0.000	0.010	0.018	0.030	0.045
		pH=7.0					
Gen	28	22	22	23	23	22	
Cef	27	20	24	24	25	23	
		pH=9.0					
Gen	28	11	10	11	12	14	
Cef	27	13	14	14	14	16	
		pH=4.0					
Gen	28	26	26	26	27	27	
Cef	27	24	24	28	28	28	

Note: The numbers in the columns indicate the zone of clearance of gentamycin and ceftriaxone in millimeters. Abbreviations: Gen - Gentamycin; Cef - Ceftriaxone.

Control is the untreated bacteria. Cef: 14-20 (Intermediate); ≥ 21 (sensitive); ≤ 13 (resistant); Gen: 13-14 (Intermediate); ≥ 21 (sensitive); ≤ 12 (resistant).

DISCUSSION

For Drug efficacy is obtained when optimal conditions of pH, temperature, and concentrations among other variables are used. This study was carried out to ascertain the response of *P. aeruginosa* exposed to GAB to variation in H. The study investigated the growth, antibiotic sensitivity, biofilm, and serum bactericidal effect on *P. aeruginosa* exposed to herbal drugs in different pH conditions.

We observed from the growth response experiment that GAB at neutral pH had inhibitory action on *P. aeruginosa* when compared with the negative control. The effect of GAB on *P. aeruginosa* in neutral conditions increased as the concentration of the GAB increased. This implies that at neutral pH, GAB possesses some antimicrobial action on *P. aeruginosa*. *C. cajan* has been reported in previous studies as an active ingredient in GAB [17,18,21] which possesses antimicrobial properties. It could be responsible for the antimicrobial action against *P. aeruginosa*. This action, however, is dependent on the concentration of GAB. There is a higher activity when the concentration of the drug is increased. In alkaline conditions, the growth of *P. aeruginosa* increased as the concentration of the drug increased. In acidic conditions, the growth of *P. aeruginosa* decreased as the concentration of GAB increased. This implies that an increase in the concentration of the drug in an acidic condition can lead to an inhibition in the growth of *P. aeruginosa*, whereas a decrease in the concentration of the drug can lead to an inhibition of the bacteria in an alkaline condition. However, in the study by Klein, it was reported that *P. aeruginosa* on exposure to acidic conditions, synthesizes a large amount of an additional phospholipid known as 2' Alanyl Phosphatidylglycerol (A-PG) [22]. This extra A-PG synthesized contributes to about 6% of the total lipid content of *P. aeruginosa* and at alkaline pH (7.3) this extra lipid layer was not present. This extra modification in the lipid membrane of *P. aeruginosa* is a process necessary for adaptation to acidic conditions.

In the antibiotic susceptibility of GAB-treated and untreated *P. aeruginosa* experiment, there are varying degrees of zones of inhibitions depending on the condition. First, a decrease in susceptibility of *P. aeruginosa* to both aminoglycoside (gentamycin) and beta-lactam (ceftriaxone) was observed in all the three conditions that were treated with GAB (control). This suggests possible induction of antibiotic resistance in *P. aeruginosa* to these antibiotics by GAB. However, at neutral and acidic pH, GAB-treated *P. aeruginosa* showed an increase in the susceptibility (to a sensitive level according to CLSI standard) to both gentamycin and ceftriaxone when compared with the negative control, at all concentrations of GAB. In alkaline pH of GAB, a decrease in susceptibility (to a resistant level according to CLSI standards) to both gentamycin and ceftriaxone was observed in all the concentrations of GAB when compared with the control. The results seen in this study may be attributed to the alteration of the outer membrane of *P. aeruginosa* by alkaline pH which could have activated resistant genes within the bacteria. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO1 has been reported to have several secretory mechanisms, TSS1-6, SecA (ATPase), SecYEG among others to transport proteins and molecules across the membrane [23,24]. This could result in a reduction in the intracellular accumulation of antibiotics thereby causing resistance.

Since the first component of the bacterial cell to be affected by a change in pH is the cell wall, membrane, proteins, and enzymes are denatured in extreme pH leading to alteration in

the ionic charges in the bacterial cell which results in the loss of the catalytic properties of the enzymes and halt in metabolism [12]. Multidrug efflux pumps, the main agent of resistance in *P. aeruginosa* are protein complexes and found in the outer membrane of the bacterial cell. Acidic and alkaline pH of the GAB may have disrupted or denatured these pumps thereby inhibiting the role of these pumps in resistance. Acidic or alkaline pH of GAB may have induced mutation in *P. aeruginosa* resulting in the susceptibility of the bacteria to antibiotics. Mutations of the cytoplasmic face of mexB can affect the transport of drugs to the targets on the cell [25]. Furthermore, certain extracts from plants serve as Efflux Pump Inhibitors (EPI) such that though the efflux pump is present since it is not active, the resistance of the bacteria to antibiotics is inhibited [26]. In contrast, Klein, reported that the modification of the lipid due to A-PG in *P. aeruginosa* leads to a reduction in the binding capacity for CAMPs, thereby obstructing the first step of antimicrobial action [22]. Also, the incorporation of A-PG changes the total membrane permeability of *P. aeruginosa* thus preventing the disintegration of the membrane structure [22].

In the crystal violet biofilm assay, it was observed that at neutral pH, GAB-treated *P. aeruginosa* formed higher biofilm levels compared to the unsupplemented control. The absorbance of the biofilm decreased as the concentration of GAD decreased. There was biofilm formation at both alkaline and acidic pH of GAB-treated *P. aeruginosa*, the absorbance of the biofilm decreased as the concentration of GAB used decreased in both cases which were similar to the observation neutral condition. This implies that at an increased concentration of GAB, *P. aeruginosa* formed more biofilm to resist the harsh effect of the drug. However, Sun et al., reported that modified flavonoids gotten from herbal drugs inhibit the formation of biofilm by *P. aeruginosa* at higher concentrations by inhibiting its type IV pili [27].

The study experimented with serum-based clearance of *P. aeruginosa* treated with the herbal drug in different pH-induced conditions. The serum bactericidal assay evaluates the bactericidal functionality of complement in the serum. Complement proteins destroy the bacterial cells via the production of membrane attack complex using the C₁-C₉ proteins [28]. The trend graph indicates serum destruction of the bacteria which continued until the 36 h and further rise was noted for both negative control and acid conditions but not the alkaline pH. Comparisons of microbial levels at 36 h, which showed the maximum level of bactericidal effect of serum, showed that the highest bacteria growth level was observed in the alkaline condition followed by the acid pH and then negative control. These results suggest that either extreme of the pH could induce serum-based resistance. Polyudova, also observed the inhibitory effect of some metals, calcium, and magnesium on *Cutibacterium (Propionibacterium) acnes* [29].

CONCLUSION

In the light of these data, we can say that lower pH conditions (acidic [pH 4.0] and alkaline [pH 7.0]) reduced the *P. aeruginosa* growth the most but induced the highest levels of biofilm and serum resistance compared to the control in a concentration-dependent manner. The alkaline conditions induce resistance to the bacteria while the acid conditions maintain the sensitivity level as observed in the control. This implies that when this herbal drug is consumed, in the acidic stomach *P. aeruginosa* becomes sensitive to gentamycin and ceftriaxone but resistant in the large intestine that is more alkaline.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Abbey, SD and Monsi, TP designed the study. Monsi, TP and Egeolu, MN carried out the laboratory experiments and managed the literature searches. Monsi, TP and Amala, SE performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol. MTP and Abbey, SD wrote the first draft of the manuscript and managed the analyses of the study. Abbey, SD supervised the work and ensured integrity of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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